

The Image Of The People With Disabilities In The Arabic Language Curriculum For The Fifth And Sixth Grades Of Basic Education In Jordan: An Analytical Study

Zain Alkaid

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 03, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Disabled Persons; School Textbook</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4815980</p>	<p><i>The current study aimed to identify the image of the People with disabilities in the Arabic language textbook for the fifth and sixth grades: An analytic study. The researcher highlighted this image within the curriculum of the Ministry of Education in Jordan for the academic year 2020/2021. The study sample comprised Arabic language textbooks for the fifth and sixth grades. To achieve the objective of the study, the researcher designed an instrument to analyse the curriculum. This instrument comprised two domains; the first domain tackled the type of disability. The second one dealt with the general characteristics of disability. Each domain included eight sub-dimensions. Indications of validity and reliability were sufficiently extracted to justify the use of the instrument. The results of the "disability type" indicated that the type of disability was not mentioned in both curricula except in two vocabulary items under the name "blind". The word "blind" was accidentally mentioned in the sixth grade textbook, the second part and not on disability purpose. Regarding the second domain of the general characteristics of disability, the results showed that none of the characteristics of the disabled was addressed in both curricula.</i></p>

Introduction

Education contributes in building inclusive and democratic communities who can be freely expressed about their differences of opinion and perspectives, seeking for achieving social unity and acceptance of diversity. Accordingly, Education increases awareness among members of society, achieving sustainable development, working to create safe and constant societies, and reduces poverty. Knowledge is the light that may be whitened the individual's life, as it is the basis of the happiness of the individual and the well-being and progress of society. With knowledge, civilizations arose and life progressed in all fields, and education is one of the indispensable necessities of life and It is the cure for ignorance and illiteracy.

With the development of life, a person needs a place to learn for individuals in their early stages of life, and these individuals need people to teach them at a level of competence and experience, and from here schools began to emerge and developed to become one of the most important pillars of societies and an important and indispensable institution.

The school is considered one of the institutions of socialization, created by society to achieve its goals, and it has been entrusted with the education and training of the individual at the level of different age and educational stages, preparing him for life physically, psychologically, socially, morally and spiritually, and personalize it with a social character. Society and awareness of its positive role in solving its problems, and the school fulfills its mission through educational curricula, as it is its tool for building the individual and bringing him up effectively. (Al-Ezzi, 2018)

The curriculum is also at the top of the educational system of any educational system. It is the core and basis of education. This is because any educational reform is not carried out in isolation from the development of the school curriculum, by virtue of it being the main focus of the educational process and its realistic embodiment of it. (BouknadelAbdellatif, 2021).

The school curriculum is: the constitution on which the educational process runs or the plan that guides this process. Therefore, modern curricula sought to ensure that the human being is the focus of the educational process, and since man is a social being, education was based on a social basis, according to which societies were keen to achieve education By raising the generations on the desired behavior in society. Marei, and the Resource(2004) .

Hence, we realize the necessity to relationship of the school curriculum with social change and keep pace with its various manifestations and problems. Among the things that the curricula must take into account: The curriculum is concerned with what children have learned within their families before they join the school so that

it can correct what they may have errors, and take into account the level of maturity that they have. The curriculum has reached students, his needs, inclinations, and preparations (Saliha al-Mahdi, 2018).

Building a valuable system among students makes them more relevant to their reality and society, more interested in its problems, and more willing to interact with it and develop it (Al-Ezzi, 2018). Curricula and textbooks are the building blocks of inclusive education systems. Curricula must include all groups at risk of exclusion, both in terms of content and implementation. Textbooks, as a component of the school curriculum, can overlook or underrepresent the characteristics of groups. Books can also perpetuate stereotypes and undermine any claim to inclusion. The handicapped are considered from the minority community according to the prevalence rates in the community, which were not represented in the curriculum. Hence, it is imperative that the curriculum address this category as the most important educational tool in changing attitudes and imparting different values. The curriculum can be defined as a "coherent and compatible network. Working together to achieve specific learning outcomes or is simply a "learning plan" (Klodiana Kolomito, 2017).

Shao-Wen Su (2012, defined school curricula as a means to achieve specific educational goals and objectives. With the many differences in determining what the curriculum is, the curriculum in its broadest sense considers everything that happens in the context of planning, teaching and learning in an educational institution (Esayas W / Tinsae, 2016). The word curriculum refers to the curriculum or training, and then the matter continued after that. The word curriculum means the content of the study materials and plans. Its own, or curriculum, means the way an individual pursues a certain goal. What knowledge is taught in the school to provide learners with information in the classroom in preparation for passing school exams' (Al-Ezzi, Hussein, 2018).

The curriculum and its relationship to society: The curriculum has a responsibility to build and maintain the identity of the community. With regard to social interactions, relationships and ties: The members of society and its institutions permanently deal with each other. The school curriculum is responsible for developing the skills of bearing responsibility, respecting others, trusting in him, dealing with him, and exchanging services and needs with him, as well as the curriculum responsible for social change as it is based on preparing students to accept changes and intervene to direct them towards positivity. With regard to the role of the curriculum in human rights issues, on the modern school curriculum, in the need to pay attention to the role of women. The role of the child. The environment, its protection and the preservation of its balance. The school curriculum is responsible for explaining cultural and social changes. Accelerating the processes of change and even leading them while preserving the constants that define the identity of individuals and groups (Obaidat, Abu Al Sameed, 2017).

Social institutions and their relationship to the school curriculum: Social institutions represent the actual embodiment of social systems and their functions, and there are many institutions in society, the most important of which are: the religious establishment, the entertainment institution, , the educational institution: It plays an important and dangerous role in rising generations of the workers' establishment, qualifying them with knowledge and several sciences . Clarifying the curriculum for the role of these institutions leads to the learners 'appreciation of the services provided by these institutions, which gives them positive attitudes towards them in a way that pushes them to search for how to benefit from them, respect their rules and preserve their facilities. (HE and Ibrahim, 2011) What matters to us in this regard is the educational institution, especially schools, and the role of the curriculum in it.

That is why the educational curriculum has been a serious social responsibility, thanks to the place it occupies in the educational process

The pedagogy itself on the one hand, thanks to what the social system relies on in achieving basic assumptions to confront accelerated social changes, and the educational curriculum assumes many social functions that are important in building and maintaining society, preserving its existence, development and achieving its goals, including the educational curriculum is the means of society and education in achieving its educational goals, the educational curriculum is the appropriate way to prepare individuals for a contemporary society with all its components, and the future society. The environment in which individuals are placed in a normal framework, the curriculum represents the trends of society and its bodies. The curriculum expresses the trends, tendencies and aspirations of society, its values and heritage. The curriculum represents the cognitive model for building the personality of the individual and the group. The curriculum represents the mechanism of society in maximizing the role of the individual and his productivity. This calls for the curriculum to include Education in all stages of the study, especially the middle stage in which the student is in adolescence, where personality is built and a pattern of behavior is crystallized in which society is supposed to go along with identifying the basic needs of the individual and society, working on the integration of educational experience that relates to the spirit of teamwork, realizing that a scientist Today has changed the world of the future (Al-Wahidi, 2017).

The researcher believes that the textbook is one of the elements of the educational curriculum, as it was considered the applied aspect of the educational curriculum, and it is the responsibility of the textbook to educate young people, as it transmits and organizes facts and purifies them and transmits everything that has a cultural or social value. We always say if you want to make any change in society, not start from looking at the

curriculum and the teacher, because it is with them that you perform miracles if they are given enough attention, and with them civilizations are destroyed if they are neglected and not given enough attention.

In Hayden, Prince, (2020) study, which aimed to find out the disabling of ability: disability representations based on strengths in children's picture books, the study sample consisted of 34 model picture books showing a main character with disabilities, and a qualitative analysis of the content of the books was analyzed. The study found that children's culture has a strong influence on the cultural structure, and it is extremely important for all children to see themselves represented by the books in their classrooms. The study also found that opinions largely based on characters with special needs are rare in children's picture books, which means that children with disabilities may not see a reflection of themselves and their personalities in the books in their classrooms, and even worse, books may reinforce adherence to stereotypes and myths about people with disabilities and their lives. Low-prevalence disabilities such as visual impairment are represented more frequently than high-prevalence disabilities. Such as a specific learning disability

Nayef (2019) conducted a study aimed at determining the effectiveness of teaching an introduction to special education course in improving attitudes towards the handicapped among a sample of Ajloun National University students. The experimental approach was followed on the one-group method, and applying the pre and post scale of attitudes towards the disabled was done. The study revealed the following results: - The students' attitudes towards the disabled were negative. - There were no statistically significant differences ($0.05 = \alpha$) due to the gender variable in all dimensions and in the tool as a whole. - There were statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the pre and post application of the study sample on the scale of attitudes towards the disabled in all dimensions and in the overall degree. The differences came in favor of the post application.

Key Words: Introduction to Special Education Course, Attitudes Toward the Disabled.

Martínez-Bello (2018), which aimed to analyze gender, age, and disability representations in music education textbooks. By analyzing the content of illustrations in textbooks for music education by following the coding scheme developed by the research team according to guidelines from previous studies on the portrayal of women and girls in textbooks in the Middle East during two periods of Spanish democracy: Prior (1992-2005) And after (2006-2015). The most important findings of the study and with regard to disability. The results indicated that the actual absence of females and males with disabilities indicates that this aspect of inclusion is still pending.

As for the study of Baad, Muhammad Al-Khalis (2016). And which aimed to know the image of the disabled in the Palestinian Arabic language curriculum for the primary stage (1-4), the method of content analysis was used. One of the most important findings of the study was the state of exclusion that people with disabilities are exposed to in the lessons.

Al-Saoub, Mutasim (2016), conducted a study aimed at showing the effect of teaching a course on rehabilitation for people with special needs in improving students' attitudes towards the disabled among a sample of students of the College of Sports Sciences, majoring in Sports Rehabilitation. The sample of the study consisted of 88 male and female students enrolled in the Special Needs Rehabilitation course. The pre and post scale of the trend scale towards the disabled, developed by Al Quraiti (1992) and applied to the Egyptian environment and used by Abu Darwish (2007), was applied to the Jordanian environment, where the study showed statistically significant differences in students' attitudes towards the disabled, as it was found that there is an improvement in students' attitudes. Towards the disabled after studying the course of rehabilitation for people with special needs. There are no statistically significant differences in the students' attitudes towards the disabled due to the variables of gender and academic achievement

In the study for Dwikat, and Maghribi (2014). And which aimed at the extent to which the rights of persons with disabilities were included in the Palestinian civic education curriculum in the lower elementary stage - the preparation stage of grades (1-4). The content analysis method was used. The results of the study showed that there is a clear lack of all rights pertaining to persons with disabilities in the civic education curriculum, as well as showing specific stereotypes of movement and visual impairment.

Al-Abadi and Al-Taj (2014) indicated in their study, which aimed to find out the image of people with disabilities in the Jordanian textbook in the pre-school stage and the first four basic grades, an analytical study. The results of the study showed that reference to people with disabilities was very rare, as indicated by the shortcomings in proposing the concept Disability, as it turns out that the disabilities that have been referred to are: mental, visual, and physical disabilities only.

In hodkinson (2005). The image of persons with disabilities and the handicapped who were portrayed in the textbooks presented to primary school students in English schools, and the study is an analysis of the image of disability on a sample of 96 textbooks. it was published between 1974 and 2005, the study found an observation that the textbook model has a limited disability structure, and indicates that there is a cultural predominance of people without disabilities within the textbook that is commonly introduced to primary stage,

Concluding Remarks:

Accordingly, the researcher believes that this study came to identify the perception of the disabled in the Arabic language curriculum for the fifth and sixth primary grades, due to the importance of the Arabic language

curriculum, which is considered a basic subject in all school stages and the importance of this age group that separates between late childhood and adolescence: This study came because of the lack of studies (according to the researcher's knowledge) on the subject of curriculum analysis in the field of special education, in addition to the fact that they dealt with variables that were not covered by previous studies, and also came after the Ministry of Education's decisions to include the concept of disability within the curricula, so this study is considered complementary and renewed at the same time.

The statement of the study: Individuals with disabilities of all ages are among the groups of society that most need special treatment, and they are considered one of the most banished groups in society, and they suffer from risks of bullying, abuse and prejudice, in addition to violence and abuse, so many experts and some people resort to Defenders of the rights of people with disabilities to develop some methods that limit these practices, which guarantee protection and personal safety, and the school curriculum in general and the textbook in particular is considered an effective tool in correcting negative societal perceptions towards the disabled by including the concepts of disability in the school curriculum. The book can be considered one of the most important means that increases correct and accurate knowledge of this category, and changes the incorrect negative perception of disabilities. Therefore, working on developing the textbook is one of the most works that can completely change the perception of the disabled. Al-Abadi, and Al-Taj, (2014).

The commitment of the international community in 2015 constitutes "ensuring quality, equitable and inclusive education for all and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all." (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 2020) .Based on these universal principles to protect the rights of people with disabilities, and the important role that the curriculum plays in achieving these Therefore, the researcher aimed to focus on knowing the image of people with disabilities in the Arabic language curriculum for the fifth and sixth primary grades in Jordan. The responses of this study (to answer the following inquiries:

Questions of the study

The statements of the study is to answer the following questions:

The first question: What is the image of disabled people in the fifth grade Arabic textbook in Jordan?

second question: . What is the image of disabled people in the Arabic textbook for the sixth grade in Jordan?

Purposes of the study:

Recognizing what is the image of people with disabilities in the fifth grade Arabic language curriculum in Jordan?

Recognizing what is the image of parents in the Arabic language curriculum for the sixth grade in Jordan?

the significance of studying:

After the Council of Ministers approved the draft law on the rights of persons with disabilities for the year 2016 as a culmination of the Kingdom's efforts for decades to keep abreast of developments and developments in the field of disability in terms of concepts and practices, the inclusion of persons with disabilities was considered the most important step for them to grow up in a healthy environment and not feel any kind of discrimination. Instead, they become able to explode their energies

Operational definitions:

Disabled persons : Individuals who face special living conditions due to a deficiency whether congenital or acquired, so that the child does not reach the level of ordinary children in one or more of the different areas of development.

The Arabic Language Curriculum: It is the document written under the supervision of the Ministry of Education, which is directed to students and includes content, means, methods, teaching methods, and evaluation methods. In this study, the curriculum for the Arabic language curriculum for the fifth and sixth grades is analyzed.

Design of the Study

The current study was followed the descriptive and analytical approach because of its relevance to the nature of the study.

Population of the study: The study population consisted of the Arabic language book for the basic stage.

Sample of the study: The study sample consisted of the Arabic language textbook for the fifth and sixth basic grades.

Instrument of the study

The researcher developed a list that includes two fields of disability after referring to previous studies and theoretical literature, so that each field includes several dimensions, the first (8) dimensions and the second field (8) dimensions. The researcher used the paragraph unit to know the degree of availability of each field in the aforementioned books in order to calculate, monitor, and extract the percentage for each dimension. The validity of the content analysis tool was verified after the tool was presented to a group of specialist in the special education. As the items that needed to be edited were modified and the items that were agreed upon were dropped (80%) or less (content validation)

Regarding the validity of instruments, the analysis was carried out by three researchers, the first researcher (Prof. Zain Al-Kayed, Professor, Al-Balqa Applied University, Special Education) and the second researcher

(Prof. Hayam Al-Momani, specializing in Social Studies Curricula, and the third researcher (Dr. Hanan Al-Younes / Studies Social, Al-Balqa Applied University) with a two-week time difference between the first and second analysis, and the consistency was calculated between the first and second time in order to extract the coefficient of agreement between them, and an agreement was found between them at a rate of (97%) and that was (using the Holste equation (1)

The procedures of the study

In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher followed the following steps:

- Defining the statement of study and its questions.
- Reading theoretical literature and previous studies related to analyzing the image of the disabled in the curriculum.
- Analysis of the Arabic language book for the fifth and sixth grades. In light of the type of disability and the characteristics of the disability (cognitive, motor, social, emotional, linguistic. By choosing the unit of analysis the paragraph by the researcher
- Determine the study community and then choose a representative sample of the study community

Frequencies were monitored to find out the degree of availability in light of the type of disability and the characteristics of the disability (cognitive, motor, social, emotional, and linguistic).

Statistical treatment: To answer the study's questions, the researcher analyzed the Arabic language book for the fifth and sixth grades, based on a developed list that consists of two areas, each area includes eight dimensions.

Frequencies and percentages were calculated in order to find out the availability of a picture of the disabled in the curriculum within the fields of study.

Discussion the results of the study

To answer the first question, which is what is the image of disabled people in the fifth grade Arabic textbook in Jordan?

The content of the fifth grade Arabic language textbook was analyzed in light of the disability type criterion, which consists of eight dimensions. Table No. (1) shows the results of the analysis for the fifth grade Arabic language textbook according to the type of disability. Frequency and percentage of mentioning types of disabilities in the Arabic language curriculum, first and second semester, The results were as follows: Frequently mentioned mental disability (0). Frequency of mention of visual impairment (0), repeated mention of hearing impairment (0), repeated mention of health and physical disability (0), repeated mention of autism (0), repeated mention of behavioral and emotional disorders (0), repeated mention of learning difficulties (0), repeated mention of lack of attention and activity overload (0).

Frequencies and percentages of disability features in the Arabic language textbook for the fifth grade, first and second semester

The second area / general characteristics of disability	Part one	percentage	Part two	Percentage	Total summation
Use the dialogue	0	0%	0	0%	0%
Reading and writing skills	0	0%	0	0%	0%
Training skills	0	0%	0	0%	0%
Social vocalizations	0	0%	0	0%	0%
Take care of yourself	0	0%	0	0%	0%
Participation in events(all levels)	0	0%	0	0%	0%
Social adaptation	0	0%	0	0%	0%
Professional qualification	0	0%	0	0%	0%
Supporting tools	0	0%	0	0%	0%

Frequency and percentage of mentioning the characteristics of disabilities in the Arabic language curriculum, first and second semester. The results were as follows: Frequent mention of using dialogue (0), repetition of reading and writing skills (0), repetition of training skills (0), repetition of social vocabulary (0), repetition of self-care (0), repeated participation in activities (0), repetition -Social adaptation (0), repetition of vocational training (0), repetition of supporting tools..(0)

To answer the second question that is what is the image of disabled people in the Arabic textbook for the sixth grade in Jordan?

The content of the Arabic text book for the sixth grade was analyzed in light of the disability type criterion, which consisted of eight dimensions

Frequencies and percentages of types of disability in the Arabic language textbook for the sixth grade, first and second semester. Table No. (3)

The first filed / types of disability	Part one	The percentage	Part two	The percentage	Total summation
---------------------------------------	----------	----------------	----------	----------------	-----------------

Mental handicap	0	0%	0	0%	0%
Visual disability	0	0%	2	1%	0%
Hearing disability	0	0%	0	0%	0%
Health and physical disability	0	0%	0	0%	0%
Autism	0	0%	0	0%	0%
Communicating disorders	0	0%	0	0%	0%
Behavioral and emotional disorders		0%	0	0%	0%
Learning difficulties	0	0%	0	0%	0%
Impaired attention and hyperactivity	0	0%	0	0%	0%

Frequency and percentage of mentioning types of disabilities in the Arabic language curriculum, first and second semester. The results were as follows: Frequently mentioned mental disability (0). Frequency of mention of visual disabled (2), repeated mention of hearing impairment (0), repeated mention of health and physical disability (0), repeated mention of autism (0), repeated mention of behavioral and emotional disorders (0), repeated mention of learning difficulties (0), repeated mention of lack of attention and activity overload.(0)

In table four frequency and percentage of mentioning the features of disabilities in the Arabic language curriculum, first and second semester. The results were as follows: Frequent mention of using dialogue (0), repetition of reading and writing skills (0), repetition of training skills (0), repetition of social vocabulary (0), repetition of self-care (0), repeated participation in activities (0), repetition Social adaptation (0), repetition of vocational training (0), repetition of supporting tools (0).

Discussion of the results:To answer the first question: What is the image of people with disabilities in the fifth grade Arabic language curriculum in Jordan? The frequency and percentage of mentioning types of disabilities were calculated in the Arabic Language Curriculum, first and second semester. According to the results, it was found that there is no mention of any type of disability in the Arabic language textbook for the fifth grade, the first part and the second part. Regarding the second area, the results were as follows: Frequency and percentage of mentioning the characteristics of disabilities in the Arabic language curriculum, first and second semester. By reviewing the results, it was found that no feature of disability was addressed, in general or in particular. The results of this study agreed with the study of each dimension, Muhammad al-Khalis (2016). Which aimed to know the image of the handicapped in the Palestinian Arabic language curriculum for the primary stage (1-4), and whose results indicated that the mention of the disabled in the curriculum was permanently excluded.

And to answer the second question, which is: What is the image of people with disabilities in the Arabic language curriculum for the sixth grade in Jordan?

Repetition of what is related to the percentage of characteristics of disabilities in the Arabic language curriculum, first and second semester.

By reviewing the results of the second question, it becomes clear that there was no mention of disability, whether the type of disability or the characteristics of disability, except for mentioning visual impairment in two locations, and in the lesson "Two Stances in the Life of the Companions", Sixth Grade, second semester, Unit Ten, the visual impairment was mentioned as a blind old woman .(13)

In this study, which was conducted in the year (2020/2021), the Arabic language curriculum was reviewed, which is the basic curriculum for all educational levels, which formed committees to integrate the concept of disability in the curriculum to facilitate the integration of the disabled academically and socially, the study did not find any mention even at the level of the concept of any disability Of disabilities. What are these trends and what is that work? Was the matter only directed at the media, and if it was true, then what do we not find in two very important academic stages?

Therefore, the Ministry of Education should collaborate with other ministries, national governments, and non-governmental partners, and link levels of education to promote inclusion. Asymmetric services, communication protocols, inadequate coordination efforts, insufficient funding and capacities lead to poor implementation and weak accountability. The right to education is a universal right recognized by international human rights law, and thus applies to all persons, including those with disabilities

Conclusions:

The image of people with disabilities wasn't addressed in all dimensions, whether in the fifth grade curriculum or the sixth grade curriculum.

Recommendations:

1. The necessity for the Ministry of Education to adopt an action plan to amend the school curricula so that the concept of disability is included in the school curricula.
2. The legislative authority monitors the implementation of laws for individuals with disabilities and obliges institutions to abide by these laws and form follow-up committees for this purpose.

References

Ahmad, Mar'i, Al-Hailah, Mahmoud. (2004). *Modern educational curricula*. Amman: Dar Al-Masirah for Publishing and Distribution.

- Al-Abbadi, Alia, Al-Taj, Hiyam . (2014). The image of people with disabilities in the Jordanian textbook in pre-school. *Education Journal of Al-Azhar University*, 2 (158)
- Al-Hussain, Azizi. (2018). *Educational curricula and their role in building the value system for pupils in early adolescence. A field study for fourth-grade intermediate pupils in Bou Saada city*. Mohamed Boudiaf Al-Messila University.
- Al-Khalis, Mohammad . (2016). The image of the child in the Palestinian Arabic language curriculum for the primary stage (1-4). *Journal of Al-Quds Open University for Research, Educational, and Psychological Studies*, 4 (14)
- Al-Khouli, Mohammad . (2011). *Curriculum foundations, design, development and evaluation*. Jordan: Dar Al Falah for Publishing and Distribution.
- Al-Saoub, Mutassim. (2016). The effect of teaching a course for people with special needs in improving attitudes towards the handicapped in a sample of Mu'tah University students. *Education Journal of Al-Azhar University*, 3(168),
- Al-Sawalmeh, Mohammad, Al-Ayasrah, Mohammad. (2014). The effectiveness of teaching the mental disability course in improving attitudes towards the mentally handicapped among a sample of female students specializing in special education at Ajloun University College in Jordan. *Journal of Educational Sciences*, 2 (4),
- A'mr, Ziyad, Abu Kamal, Mahmoud. (2010). *Study on the disabled persons' Issues in the school textbook*. Palestine: Qadir Foundation for Social Development.
- Fawzy, Lohaidi. (2017). The social basis of the educational curriculum. *Al-Sarraj Magazine in Education and Community issues*, (1),
- Hashem, Marwa. (2020). *Curriculum , textbook, elements of the educational process*. Baghdad: Al-Mustansiriya University, College of Basic Education, Department of Mathematics, Graduate Studies, Methods of Teaching Mathematics.
- Nayef, Wahsha, Ali, and Wahsha .(2019). The effectiveness of teaching an introduction to special education course in improving attitudes towards the handicapped among a sample of students from Ajloun National University. *Laboratory for the Development of Psychological and Educational Practices*, 12(1), 152-171.
- Obaidat, Thouqan, Abu Al -Sameed, Suhaila. (2017). *Teaching strategies in the twenty-first century : Teacher's guide, the educational supervisor, and the practical education guide for students – teachers*. Amman: Al-Fikr House for Publishing and Distribution.
- Sa'adeh, Judeh, Ibrahim, Abdullah. (2011). *The contemporary school curriculum*. Amman: Al- Fikr House for Publishing and Distribution.
- UNESCO.(2020). *General learning monitoring report, inclusive education for all: Everyone is without exception*.
- The United Nations. (2013). *Human Rights Council, twenty-fifth session, items 2 and 3 of the agenda, annual report of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, reports of the High Commissioner and the Secretary-General, promoting and protecting all human rights, civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights, including the right to development*.

المراجع الانجليزية:

- Alan Hodkinsona, Amir Ghajariehb and Ali Salam(2016)**An analysis of the cultural representation of disability in school textbooks in Iran and England**,<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/03004279.2016.1168861>
- Esayas W/Tinsae, (2016) *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Social Sciences* ISSN 2249-9482, Impact Factor: 6.301, Volume 6 Issue 04, April 2016.
- Klodiana, Kolomitro(2017). *Curriculum Design Handbook*, Center for teaching and learning.queens university.
- Hayden, H. Emily, and Angela M.T. Prince. "Disrupting ableism: Strengths-based representations of disability in children's picture books." *Journal of Early Childhood Literacy* (2020): 1468798420981751. DOI: 10.1177%2F1468798420981751. Reprinted by permission of SAGE Publications.
- This.
- Hodkiinson,Alan(2005). inclusive education and culturalr representation of disability and disabled people within the english education system critical examination of the mediating influence of primary school, e-Jornal, Volume 1 N0.1
- Mª del Mar Bernabé-Villodre, Vladimir E. Martínez-Bello(2018), Analysis of gender, age and disability representation in music education textbooks: A research update, First Published April 25, 2018 Research Article
- Secombe, J (2007) Attitudes Towards Disability in an Undergraduate Nursing Curriculum: The Effects of a Curriculum Change, Code.<http://www.coda.ac.nz/ucol n jo/1>
- Services for People with Special Needs",(2012). www.kidpower.org, Retrieved 15-2-2020. Edited.
- Shao-Wen Su, *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 153-158, January 2012 © 2012 ACADEMY PUBLISHER Manufactured in Finland.doi:10.4304/jltr.3.1.153-158

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0255761418763900>.

Author Information

Dr. Zain Alkaid

Assistant Professor / Al-Balqa Applied University
